

Japan Journal of Geopolitical Research

Japan Association for Geopolitical Research

ISSN 2758-7851

Volume 2, January 2024

The Politicisation of Sexual Violence in Ukraine: The Impact of Partisan Representation on Effective Responses.

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ABSTRACT

Conflict-based sexual violence refers to the additional layer of complexity that exists regarding coerced sexual acts that occur within the chaos, disorder, and militarisation of conflict zones. Frequently, the political factors that permeate such conflicts will make these sensitive crimes even more difficult to investigate. Narratives of reflexive patriotism or deliberate propaganda which lionise one side of a conflict or demonise another, can lead to the issue becoming a tool in propaganda campaigns between opposing sides. Following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, conflict-based sexual violence has been presented in Western media as a crime specific to Russian forces. While almost certainly true in some cases, several factors suggest that the issue has become politicised in a manner which prioritises political narratives over the protection of vulnerable women. This paper argues that enough evidence of such politicisation exists to warrant a change in how the relevant international agencies and the mass media approach the issue, with a higher standard of neutral assessment being required to advance the welfare of women in the conflict zone.

Keywords: *Ukraine, Russia, gender-violence, conflict-based sexual violence, rape, sexual assault, propaganda*

Introduction

Sexual violence is a reliable concomitant of war. It varies in intensity depending upon the political and cultural elements at play but where conflict exists the danger of rape and sexual assault become exponentially higher. Despite the severity of the problem and the explicit harm to victims, in some cases responses to the problem do little to safeguard the welfare of such individuals and instead focus on politicising the issue (Meger, 2016), framing the problem as a tool for political, rather than civil or humanitarian, action.

Throughout the conflict in Ukraine that began in early 2022, there has been a significant focus by Western media on the issue of conflict-based sexual violence. However, a significant amount of this coverage has taken the form of political communication, propaganda, rather than an actual response to the very real and serious problem of sexual violence in the region. This article examines this coverage and argues that the partisan nature of much of the content, and the political agendas that lie behind it, are characteristic of a level of politicisation which is likely to compromise, rather than safeguard, the welfare of past and future victims. The purpose of the paper is not to prove that politicisation has occurred, as the subjective nature of political communication makes that impossible to definitively state. Rather, it is to show that the evidence of politicisation, and the influence of the filter through which it skews perception of the issue, needs to be taken into account by concerned governments, NGOs and the public themselves, in order to truly understand and address the very real underlying problems.

A Brief History of Atrocity Propaganda

In warfare there are two types of enemy behaviour proven to stir widespread national anger. One is crimes against children, like claims of the Irish murdering English babies in the 1600s (Read, 1938, 234), German soldiers mutilating Belgian children during the First World War (Marquis, 1978, 486), or the Syria government killing its own children more recently (Boyd Barrett, 2022, 226). The other is the crime of rape, an attack on the safety, purity, and honour of the women men are traditionally expected to defend. In the ancient world Greek and Roman historians have presented ‘conquest rape’ as being a widespread practice, with soldiers under order to assault the women of defeated states (Madenholm, 2022). In WWII the Japanese, the Russians, and the Germans were all portrayed at various times as being proponents of rape as a strategy of war. However, less attention was given to the behaviour of the victor and the sexual violence committed by French, British, and American troops against German women (Gebhardt, 2017) and Japanese women (Shrivers, 2005, 212) in the last days, and aftermath of World War Two.

In the recent Ukraine War, we have both elements, the harm of children and rape as a military strategy, being portrayed as a singularly Russian crime. It would have been surprising if such headlines had not appeared, as they have become a common element of the modern propaganda playbook. Prior to and during NATO’s intervention in Kosovo in 1999, at that time still unsubstantiated reports of “rape camps” were used to justify military attacks that cost civilian lives (Clark, 2003). Both before and during the US invasion of Iraq, American stories of “rape rooms” were one element of the claim for a humanitarian justification for the illegal military intervention (Saletan, 2004). In the 2011 NATO intervention in Libya, baseless tales of government troops being equipped with Viagra to enable greater amounts of rape were widespread in the media, including equally unfounded allegations that children were targeted (Kolmasoya and Krulisova, 2019). Similar claims that rape was being employed explicitly as a tool of war were also made against the Syrian government during the civil war that began in 2011 (Boyd Barrett, 2022, 197).

Even regarding purely potential foes, where direct conflict has not yet begun, claims of widespread use of sexual violence are common in Western media, such as claims that North Korea employs such tactics against its own bureaucrats (HRW, 2018) and soldiers (Mohan, 2017). As such, it would be almost strange not to see similar allegations being levelled against Russia in regard to its conduct during the Ukraine War.

The Reality of Conflict-Based Sexual Violence

It is perhaps not always true that rape is exacerbated by war, nor that all armies engage in it. Some authors (Sussman, 2011) argue that draconian military control or cultural factors can reduce the incidence rate. Yet,

these arguments themselves often have a political element and, even where they might prove true, such exceptions are fleetingly rare when weighed against the ample evidence for its near omnipresence as a military malaise. In the USA, a frequent proponent of stories that focus on other state's problematic sexual conduct, one in four US military personnel report being sexually assaulted during their service (Moyer, 2021), while the annual rate of incidence is reported to be more than 20,000 cases per year, or more than 50 separate sexual assaults in the US military every day (PBS, 2021). We can see, therefore, than even in militaries where the surrounding political culture exhibits a strong awareness of, and encourages a firm response to, issues of sexual violence, it can still manifest as an endemic problem in their military forces.

During the Yugoslav Wars of the 1990s, feminist groups campaigned, unsuccessfully, to highlight the fact that rape was committed by all soldiers in the region, and that victims came from all sides. In fact, very often the violence came from soldiers on the victim's own side. They found that Western media were often unconcerned with or unwilling to highlight the suffering of Serbian victims of sexual violence, favouring instead a portrayal of attacks against Slovenian, Croatian, and Bosnian women as coming exclusively from one side of the conflict (Simic, 2016). In actuality, soldiers on leave, and ex-soldiers, frequently raped women from their own side. Doja (2019, 547) describes the manner in which this complex situation was presented in less than balanced terms:

One of the most disturbing aspects of war rape in former Yugoslavia is the special explosion of extensive media coverage surrounding the sensationalized reporting of systematic mass rape, sexual violence and other war atrocities, aimed to amplify nationalist fervour, rather than to help the traumatized women...Indeed, many worried about the fact that some of the media coverage appeared to have taken on a life of its own, creating a kind of hysteria far from the experience of the individual victims.

The issue is further compounded by the possibility of deception or false testimony. Pierre (2018) presents rape, including false allegations of crimes, as a potential tool of information warfare that can be used asymmetrically by the weak against stronger foes.

Other reasons why false testimony might occur include a belief that perceived shame can be mitigated by being seen as a victim of 'the other', doubt that authorities will investigate crimes committed by their own side, or fear of retribution for bringing negative attention to your own side. Prior to the Ukraine War, the UK government acknowledged these facts in a handbook that established protocols for the handling of sexual violence investigations in conflict zones. The book explicitly encouraged investigators to remember that false claims might additionally be motivated by a desire to gain privileged access to humanitarian aid, and that the accuracy and honesty of testimony might be compromised by political agendas (UKFCDO, 2014, 218). When examining the issue of sexual violence in Ukraine it is worth considering whether these standards are being adhered to.

The Case of Ukraine

Before examining the issue of sexual violence during the current stage of the conflict in Ukraine it is worth looking at the pre-existing problems in this region. A 2019 study by the Organisation for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) found that two-thirds of Ukrainian women had reported being victims of psychological, physical, or sexual violence. The gender norms of the country show a significant tolerance for such behaviour with 51% of women saying that their peers would agree that "it's important for a man to show his partner who's boss," and almost one in five (19%) stating that sexual intercourse with a woman without her consent is justified if it occurs within a couple or between cohabiting partners. Almost one in four women (24%) placed blame on the victims of domestic violence, believing that it is often instigated by the victims themselves. Finally, abusive behaviour was significantly more likely to be suffered by women whose partners were currently or previously engaged in combat (OSCE, 2019, iii-iv).

Looking specifically at sexual violence in the Donbass region between 2014 and 2017, a United Nations report found that all sides in the conflict had perpetrated acts of sexual violence but there were no grounds to believe that rape was being used for tactical or strategic purposes by either side (UNHCR, 2017, 3). The report

did, however, find that:

In territory controlled by the Government of Ukraine, OHCHR identified a pattern of sexual violence perpetrated in places of detention against individuals perceived to be a part of, or affiliated with armed groups, in order to punish and humiliate them, and/or extract confessions from them (UNHCR, 2017, 15).

It also stated that the Security Service of Ukraine (SBU) in many cases employed:

Sexual violence (that) amounted to torture, causing severe physical pain and mental suffering. Rape, threats of rape, beatings and electrocution of genitals were often used as an interrogation technique (UNHCR, 2017, 16).

This behaviour was certainly not exclusive to the Ukrainian government forces, with similar acts perpetrated by the armed groups opposing them at the time in the Donbass region, but rather should be taken as evidence that troops on both sides of the line of conflict had displayed a similar capacity for human rights abuse and the use of sexual violence.

The NGO Save the Children was active in the Donbass during this stage of the conflict and their report on dangers faced by children in the region also spoke of the capacity of these troops for aggressive acts directed at the local civilian populace:

The (Ukrainian) army is not considered by residents to be their protector. Instead, it seems that people feel that either the army does not care about them or considers them to be part of the enemy. Children and adults explained that they were particularly scared when soldiers were drunk...the military actors have less control and sometimes start shooting near civilians or start fights with civilians (Hill, 2019, 21).

This threatening behaviour was often directed at young girls in a sexually aggressive manner:

Adolescent girls said that they face harassment from military men, who catcall them in the street. Some girls reported that the military stop their cars close to girls in the street and try to touch them. Other girls (from the 10-13-year old age group) reported that military men talk to them and try to make the girls go with them; they also felt that there was a risk that soldiers could drag girls somewhere in the evening (Hill, 2019, 21).

Similar findings were shown in a report by Amnesty International, who stated that they encountered several cases where soldiers offered money or alcohol in exchange for sex with girls as young as 13 (Amnesty, 2029, 64).

Deeper investigation of such incidents proved difficult, however, with one Kiev-based NGO stating, "Documenting sexual violence on government-controlled territory has been more complicated. Survivors and witnesses have been hesitant to talk about violence due to fear of reprisals (and) stigma in the community." They also noted that, "Tolerance towards such violence has also increased during the conflict." (EUCfCI, 2019, 73) In cases of intimate partner rape, women in Ukraine are generally discouraged by police from making reports (Amnesty, 2020, 46) and this is even more the case where soldiers are involved, with women pressured to change statements and feeling a lack of trust in the authorities ability or willingness to protect them from reprisals (Amnesty, 2020, 63).

Suffice to say that well before 2022, sexual violence was a widespread problem in Ukraine and it was particularly bad for partners of soldiers or civilians in areas with soldiers, from either side. These issues occasionally received attention in the Western press, for example, in the twenty years between 2000 and 2020, the Guardian newspaper had five articles whose main theme was sexual violence in Ukraine. However, following the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, the next year saw the Guardian print at least 15 separate stories whose main theme was sexual violence in Ukraine (as shown in Table 1). All of these stories focused on Russian

use, and only Russian use, of sexual violence as a military tactic. There were numerous further stories that mentioned claims of Russian rape and sexual violence without specifically focusing on those topics. And, of course, the Guardian was only one of the many western news outlets for whom this became an almost constant narrative. Given what has been previously stated regarding sexual violence in combat zones typically being perpetrated by all parties, given what has also been stated regarding the relatively high level of tolerance for sexual violence in Ukraine, and given what has been stated regarding prior reports of Ukrainian troops being involved in incidents of sexual violence or intimidation, when Russia is made the sole focus for such allegations it calls into question whether accuracy and balance are receiving a lower prioritisation than the propaganda value of such stories.

The Claims against Russia

Allegations of Russian crimes arose within the first month of the invasion, with many high-level Ukrainian government officials making unverified claims that Russian soldiers were raping women in the occupied regions (Reuters, 2022). These claims were repeated regularly throughout the Western press, often without any verification beyond “Ukrainian officials say...” and in many cases the official in question was Ukraine’s then Ombudsman for Human Rights, Lyudmila Denisova (Jankowicz, 2022; UPCfHR, 2022). These statements were, supposedly, based upon an estimated 37,000 phone calls that Denisova reported had been received by hotlines set up for victims of sexual violence in the conflict. She said that, “A fifth of the callers, which is around 200 calls per day, after sending them to psychiatrists, we confirm that they have been sexually assaulted by Russian soldiers” (Rahman, 2022).

There was little hard evidence, however, of these accusations and Denisova failed to comply with United Nations requests to forward them the evidence. In June 2022 Ukrainian newspaper *Ukrayinska Pravda* conducted an investigation that determined that Denisova had given her own daughter a job overseeing one of the hotlines for victims. Her daughter regularly shared extremely lurid stories of Russian atrocities with the press, often alleging terrible crimes against children, and claimed her hotline received, “about 1,040 calls in a month and a half. Of them, 450 related to the rape of children”, yet, when prosecutors examined the hotline records, they found it had received only 92 calls in total during its entire operation. Denisova received the same lurid stories she shared with Western press from her daughter “over tea” and she passed them on, without verification, she said, because she wanted victory for Ukraine (Lukashova, 2022). Even the veracity of the small number of calls received is questionable given that throughout the period in question, viral social media posts from gynaecologists, lawyers, and tv personalities, implored Ukrainian women to come forward with evidence of sexual violence committed by Russian troops (Ferris-Rotman, 2022).

On 31st May 2022, Denisova was removed from her position as Ombudsman, with the Deputy Chairman of the Ukrainian Parliamentary regulatory Committee, Pavlo Frolov, explaining in a Facebook post that part of the reason for this was that,

The unclear concentration of the Ombudsman's media work on the numerous details of "unnatural sexual crimes" and "rape of children" in the occupied territories that could not be confirmed by evidence, only harmed Ukraine and distracted the world media from the real needs of Ukraine (Frolov, 2022).

Despite this, more than a year later, many major Western media organisations continue to use stories based upon Denisova’s fabrications without any correction or notification to readers of her unreliability (BBC, 2022a; Ochab, 2022) and some even attempt to whitewash her statements as being something other than distortions of the truth (Vox, 2022).

Despite this blow to their reliability of their testimony, high-ranking members of the Ukrainian government continued to promote allegations of uniquely Russian use of sexual violence. At a conference on sexual violence in Britain, Olena Zelenska claimed that Russian soldiers had been ordered 'from the top' to use rape, castration, and sexual abuse of children as weapons of war. She also made the startling claim that the wives of Russian soldiers tell them, “Go on, rape those Ukrainian women” (Scott, 2022). At face value it seems ludicrous that anyone would say such things, but according to Ukrainian intelligence one Russian woman said

this to her husband on an intercepted call. There is no clear evidence of this call, but it is certainly possible. Horrible people do exist but how does one reprehensible woman become a representative of Russian wives in general, or of Russian military policy at the strategic level?

If we take the statements of individuals as a basis for universal condemnation, then what do we make of a statement by head of the State Border Service of Ukraine, Major General Sergei Deineko, who wrote, “Everyone who took part in this will be killed. Their wives, children, parents, brothers, sisters will be killed. All!!! We will kill everyone. Your entire bloodline” (Lapin, 2022). Or, we can consider Ukrainian television host Fakhrudin Sharafmal, who suggested that Adolf Eichmann showed that to kill a people you have to kill their children, and that Ukrainian civilians should be prepared to kill Russian children (CJE, 2022). Similar abhorrent statements exist on the Russian side, with Russian journalist Anton Krasovsky calling for Ukrainian children to be drowned or burned (BBC, 2022b). Yet, we recognise these are individuals and represent neither the nation’s leaders, nor its people as a whole.

In a similar manner, it is reasonable to imagine that Russia’s willingness to use convicted felons in its Wagner Private Military Company might contribute to a potential increase in sexual violence in the conflict zone. However, Ukraine also passed laws releasing convicts from prison in return for conscription. While those convicted of murder and sexual assault were exempted, the provisions included those convicted of procurement, human trafficking, brigandage, and numerous violent crimes (Sluga Naroda, 2022). In attempting a non-partisan assessment of facts, rather than looking for isolated examples that might bolster broad, emotive allegations, it is important to concentrate on what evidence of criminal activity exists at a wider level. Unsubstantiated claims, extreme individual cases, or aspersions based upon the moral character of specific groups, offer little insight as to the extent of the problem, rather, their use as political rhetoric actively contributes to further obfuscation of the issue.

The Evidence against Russia

One British expert on conflict-based sexual violence, Doctor Ingrid Elliott, claimed there were two patterns to Russian sexual violence in Ukraine: the first, following attacks on towns and villages in which civilians would be rounded up and women, “held in basements, where repeated sexual violence is inflicted upon them, for days of even weeks”, and the second in detention centres where the violence was focused more on male prisoners (Barber, 2022a).

This narrative comes from cherry-picking what are already questionable sources and portraying them in a manner that solely focuses on Russian culpability. Many similar statements are based upon fieldwork done by the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). In October 2022 it released a report examining the impact of the war on civilians (OHCHR, 2022b, 2-5). This report stated that Russian armed forces were “responsible for the vast majority of violations identified,” and listed several examples for which it relied “primarily on first-hand information, including through interviews with witnesses and victims of alleged violations.” These include individual examples of alleged crimes similar to those described by Elliot but nothing to suggest it was conducted as a strategy or solely by Russian troops. It also made it clear that it could not examine all reported incidents and chose to focus on cases based upon their gravity, ease of access, geographic location and other factors.

In terms of evidence there are numerous critical weaknesses that second-hand accounts based upon this report invariably fail to highlight. These include the fact that there is no clarification regarding the extent to which the examined violations are affected by reporting bias due to the direct participation of the Ukrainian government in facilitating meetings with alleged victims, and the Russian government’s lack of similar participation. This lack of participation is excused as follows: “attempts to establish meaningful communication with Russian Federation authorities have been unsuccessful.” (OHCHR, 2022b, 5) This state of affairs leads to significant uncertainty over the trustworthiness of these investigations. Notably, the OHCHR’s investigation focused entirely upon areas then controlled by the Ukrainian government (Kyiv, Chernihiv, Kharkiv and Sumy) raising questions of how safe victims in these areas would have felt about discussing potential crimes by Ukrainian forces, and how patterns of reporting might differ in the contested regions of Donetsk and Luhansk. Most importantly, it states that its evidentiary standard is “reasonable grounds” for belief (OHCHR, 2022b, 4).

Reasonable grounds are the least demanding level of evidence used by the International Criminal Court and other international legal entities. It is generally only used to argue that claims are strong enough to warrant further investigation rather than being dismissed, and is a lower level of evidence than “substantial grounds,” the level used to confirm charges as worthy of prosecution, and far lower than the “beyond reasonable doubt” level used to acquire convictions (Cross, 2018, 233). Despite this, the above report has repeatedly been referenced by Western media as though it constitutes proof of crimes having occurred rather than simply raising the possibility that crimes occurred.

An earlier report released by the U.N. Human Rights Monitoring Mission (OHCHR, 2022a, 34), based upon reporting from a much wider geographic area, was more even-handed in its claims, stating that of 108 allegations of crimes they had received they had only been able to verify 23 (and these only to the reasonable grounds standard). Of these 11 were alleged to have been committed by Russian troops, two by unidentified troops in Russian controlled areas, five by Ukrainian troops, and five by unidentified troops in Ukrainian controlled areas. The head of the mission, Matilda Bogner, also stated that they had, “not found evidence of the systematic use of sexual violence as a weapon of war” (Morris, 2022).

This, more even allocation of culpability, is what might be more commonly expected regarding sexual violence in a war zone: an acceptance that all sides have a potential for involvement, that individual troops in all armies are capable of such offences, and that all governments bear a similar legal responsibility for the actions of their troops in the field. The most recent report on the issue, however, still presents its findings in a manner which suggests a higher level of Russian perpetration of abuse. Over the year prior to the report, the OHCHR claimed to have documented 133 cases of sexual abuse in Russian-held territories (OHCHR, 2023, 16), and just 24 cases in Ukrainian-held territories (OHCHR, 2023, 27). In this more recent study, the forms of abuse are now significantly dominated by male victims of abuse during detention, with crimes against women mostly belonging to unjustified strip searches and threats of sexual violence. Again, it is worth considering whether the imbalance in reported figures represents either a greater propensity for such crimes by Russian troops, or further potential for selective bias in data collection and reporting in the absence of Russian government participation.

The Russian government very clearly claims the latter is the case, specifying a pre-existing bias within the OHCHR as their reason for not supporting its investigative mission. The spokesperson for Russia’s Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Maria Zakharova, stated that Russia does not recognise the authority of the OHCHR missions and views it as existing solely for the purpose of, “putting pressure on Russia, propagating false data, discrediting the Russian armed forces, as well as all kinds of whitewashing and praising of the Kyiv regime” (RMFA, 2022b). She further claimed that the report’s findings indicate a failure to recognise documented crimes committed by Ukrainian troops and that many of the staff involved in compiling their reports are Ukrainian citizens with a clear political bias.

Of course, such claims by Russia might be made regardless of the accuracy of the reports. However, this possibility of Russian bias is more frequently taken by Western sources as a certainty, with Russian viewpoints on the matter dismissed out of hand as bare-faced lies. For both sides, however, whether the claims of the OHCHR or counter claims made by the Russian government, the impact of bias should only become a factor where evidence suggests its existence is promoting selective interpretation of the facts. In the case of some United Nations staff this is demonstrable. Pramilla Patten, the UN Special Representative on Sexual Violence in Conflict stated during a media interview that, “When you hear women testify about Russian soldiers equipped with Viagra, it’s clearly a military strategy” (CNN, 2022). These statements were challenged during a leaked, private phone call in which she admitted that there was no evidence to support those claims, that Viagra was never mentioned in any UN reports, and that her statements were simply based of the testimony of “survivors and service providers” she had met “in the presence of high-ranking Ukrainian officials while she was in Kiev” (Rubenstein, 2022). This willingness not only to accept unverified statements as fact, but to further promote them through the media outlets, does not conform to the level of neutral analysis that should be expected from an organisation such as the United Nations. The Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, reasonably, likened these unsubstantiated allegations to the earlier apocryphal allegations made by Lyudmila Denisova, and the very similar disproven claims made regarding the use of Viagra during the Libyan Civil War (RMFA, 2022a).

In a separate statement, Zhakarova argued that a greater threat to Ukrainian women's security existed in the form of a significant upsurge in human trafficking of female Ukrainian refugees throughout Western Europe, and that this more pressing issue was being largely ignored in favour of promoting stories of Russian-perpetrated sexual violence (Pravda, 2022). As of July 2023, more than 8 million refugees from Ukraine were recorded across Europe, an estimated 90% of them female. Robert Biedron, the president of the EU Parliament's Women's Rights Committee, stated that, "hundreds of thousands of Ukrainian women have been victims of human trafficking. This was the case before the war and the war has only made it worse" (Cimino and Degani, 2023). An investigation by Thomson-Reuters and the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) found a significant increase, following the start of the war, in the targeting of Ukrainian women for sexual exploitation in Europe (Fischer, 2022).

Given the significant threat these patterns in trafficking represent to the safety of Ukrainian women, and the attention that conflict-based sexual violence has received, it might be expected, by members of the public, that the level of news coverage would reflect the severity and growing scope of the problem. However, if we again use Britain's Guardian newspaper as an example, we find that during the one year period from March 2022 to February 2023, where 15 separate stories promoted Russia as having a uniquely pervasive role in sexual violence in the conflict zone, there is just a single story that strongly relates to the upsurge in potential sex trafficking of Ukrainian women, and two others that have more limited relevance to the issue (Table 2).

Altogether, when we consider the extent of the evidence against Russia as being a particular perpetrator of conflict-based sexual violence (as opposed to what might be expected, based upon existing patterns, of any combatant) we find that many of the early media stories were based upon apocryphal allegations, exaggerated and promoted without any verification by individuals such as Lyudmila Denisova. We then find other stories relying upon reports from organisations like the UN OHCHR, without clearly acknowledging that these reports are based only upon 'reasonable grounds' standards of evidence, that in effect do no more than take unsupported allegations as sufficient grounds to examine matters further. We also find instances of high-ranking individuals within these supposedly neutral organisations, such as Pramilla Patten, promoting unsubstantiated rumours in a manner that is reminiscent of disproven propaganda from earlier conflicts. Finally, we find that other aspects of sexual violence against Ukrainian women, such as the significant upsurge in the number of women vulnerable to human trafficking and sexual exploitation, have received far less attention in the Western press than stories promoting Russian involvement in conflict-based sexual violence. Taken as a whole, these factors suggest at least a reasonable possibility (at least as much as the reasonable grounds of OHCHR reporting) that the issue of conflict-based sexual violence is being used and promoted for political rather than humanitarian reasons.

The Purpose of Politicising Sexual Violence

There is no doubt that sexual violence in the Ukraine conflict is a serious issue, nor that Russian troops are involved, nor that those responsible, directly or indirectly, should be punished. The question here is not in regard to such self-evident matters but rather the extent to which these issues have been politicised, a term which is generally accepted as the transporting of a non-political issue, in this case one of impartial justice, into the sphere of public politics, i.e. making it a matter of public and governmental choice, something upon which collectively binding decisions must be made (Zurn, 2019).

Evidence of such politicisation can be seen in the UK government's 'Preventing Sexual Violence in Conflict Initiative' which looks at the problem of sexual violence in Ukraine as a purely Russian crime, stating that it will, "work with the Ukrainian Government to deliver justice following the abhorrent reports of rape and sexual violence perpetrated by Russian forces" in response to what it calls "mounting evidence of rape and other heinous crimes committed by Russian forces," and "Russia's barbaric acts." As part of its response, it aims to establish an Atrocity Crimes Advisory Group (ACA) that will, "reinforce current EU, US and UK efforts to deliver accountability for atrocity crimes, including sexual violence, in the context of Russia's ongoing war of aggression against Ukraine" (UKFCDO, 2022). There is clearly no effort being made at impartiality, or the recognition of crimes of sexual violence in Ukraine by any parties other than Russia, and the British government's response seeks to make this partisan approach a matter of national public policy.

A further element of this initiative is the creation of new Sexual Violence Mobile Justice Team, “a 20-strong group of lawyers and military analysts (who) are racing to identify and prosecute Russian troops accused of rape and other acts of sexual violence.” One of the leaders of these teams declared, “we will work to ensure that those who suffer these terrible crimes are supported and that Putin’s men are brought to account” (Barber, 2022b). Again, what should be a neutral issue of legal response and humanitarian support is being framed as a selectively focused campaign against only specific, politically expedient, perpetrators.

This focus on “Putin’s men” suggests that a possible underlying motivation for such investigation, rather than targeting individual perpetrators of sexual violence, is to create a justification for charges of humanitarian crimes to be brought against Russia’s leadership. There is a view in human rights law that governments can instrumentalise sexual violence as a strategy and this has been ruled as a crime against humanity by the International Criminal Court (ICC). If Russia can be portrayed as having conducted such actions on a strategic basis, its leadership could potentially be tried at The Hague. This has already been employed in a parallel manner with charges of “the war crime of unlawful deportation of population” being used at the ICC to issue arrest warrants against Putin and other Russian officials (ICC, 2023).

These specific charges have already been challenged as being both politically motivated and unsubstantiated. The ICC warrant was based upon a report compiled by the Yale Humanitarian Research Lab, which is directly supported by the US State Department (USSD, 2023). Journalists found that much of the report’s content contradicted claims within the ICC warrant, suggesting the latter was a result of political rather than humanitarian motivations, while visits to supposed ‘re-education camps’ inside Russia revealed instead school systems with children who had been sent to them expressly with their parent’s permission (Loffredo and Blumenthal, 20223). Speaking in regard to the ICC warrant, Stephen Rapp, the former US Ambassador at Large for War Crimes, declared, “this makes Putin a pariah. If he travels, he risks arrest. This never goes away. Russia cannot gain relief from sanctions without compliance with the warrants” (Reuters, 2023). However, given the weak nature of the allegations regarding this alleged child abduction it seems unlikely this particular warrant will serve such a purpose. Fresh charges of systematic use of sexual violence as a strategy of war, however, might create a more lasting and more visceral impact.

As a non-signatory of the ICC, the charges have no legal impact on Russia or its officials but in the wider picture they can serve as justification for future sanctions, a narrative with which to further demonise Russia’s leadership, a tool of negative soft power to distance Russia from potential allies, and potentially a means of leveraging internal public pressure against Putin within Russia. In fact, the first of these has already taken place when, at a recent Preventing Sexual Violence in Conflict Initiative (PSVI) conference in London, the UK Foreign Secretary explicitly stated that sanctions would now be used as a tool to respond to crimes of sexual violence (UKGov, 2022).

The strategic benefits that can be gained through the overtly political use of these allegations might explain why, despite the lack of evidence to support it, there appears to be a widespread effort in Western media to create an impression that the Russia government has explicitly endorsed the use of sexual violence as a strategy. Examples include a US media outlet declaring that, “experts say there are indications that Russian soldiers are using rape in a number of ways - as a form of punishment, as well as with perhaps systematic, genocidal aims,” (NPR, 2022) Australian news reporting that, “stories emerging from Ukraine create an overwhelming suspicion that Russia’s military has weaponised sexual violence,” (Taylor, 2022) and, in the UK, newspapers insisting that “the world can’t ignore Russia’s use of rape as a weapon of war” (Helic, 2022).

An article by the US Hudson Institute think tank outlined the possibility of a future collapse of the Russian government and a soft coup by reformist elements who would arrest the current leadership and hold them accountable for past acts (Coffey, 2022). Multiple articles in US establishment media such as Foreign Affairs (Hathaway, 2022; Kasparov, 2022; Hathaway, 2023) and Foreign Policy (Siddiqui, 2022; Sonnenfeld, 2022; Szcwcyk, 2023) echo these views. Taken as a whole a political motivation for presenting the issue of sexual violence in Ukraine in a biased manner is by far the most understandable explanation for the one-sided nature of coverage and the overt omission of incidents of sexual violence, either perpetrated by Ukrainian troops or experienced by civilians in the pro-Russian regions.

The Harmful Impact of the Politicisation of Sexual Violence

The importance of investigating crimes of sexual violence with complete impartiality has consequences not only in relation to the use of distorted narratives as a tool of international influence, but also as a direct factor in protecting the wellbeing of victims. Any actions which manipulate or alter the reliability of testimony, which create an atmosphere in which either truthful testimony might be repressed, or dishonest testimony encouraged, invariably hamper proper investigation of such crimes. Any bias which exaggerates or focuses exclusively on the actions of one group of offenders, or which downplays or ignores the actions of other groups, can impact efforts to bring all perpetrators to justice or foster an atmosphere of impunity wherein some offenders see far less punishment, and thus inherent risk, attached to their crimes.

In discussing the needs of victims in international tribunals on sexual violence Beltz (2008, 190) highlighted the trauma victims can experience through possible rejection by their communities or by the justice system itself. In situations where such crimes have been politicised there is an added pressure for the testimony of victims to adhere to the overarching political narrative. Where their abusers do not fit the proper demographic, there is a danger of backlash from those who support the established narratives. Where the victims themselves do not belong to the correct demographic, there is a likelihood of them receiving lesser access to the mechanisms of justice.

The evidentiary standards accepted in a politicised process, whether the apocryphal tales spread by Denisova and others, or the promotion of “reasonable grounds” as being reliable standard of verification, create a danger of real crimes and real testimony losing their impact or plausibility as a result of distrust in the greater number of stories than are unsubstantiated, exaggerated, or outright lies.

A secondary impact of politicisation is the diversion of both resources and public attention from more honest and even-handed attempts to provide support for victims. Large-scale events such as the London PSVI conference create an impression that significant work is being done to address the problem. Yet, while such events may be generating some positive change, there are reasonable grounds to question the extent to which such events are motivated by political rather than humanitarian aims, how much of their time and energy is devoted purely to media campaigns and narrative building, how much to political lobbying for initiatives such as ICC prosecutions, and to what extent such political motivations detract from or divert the level of actual aid that reaches victims.

A third effect is on the broader public understanding of the issue at hand. Politicised coverage renders a complex and multifaceted problem as something far simpler and morally black and white. We have good victims and evil perpetrators, conveniently falling on clear political lines, that offer a straightforward political solution: by targeting evil leader ‘X’ we can prevent the abuse of women. Undercutting the true scope and complexity of the problem makes it more difficult to provide aid but, at the same time, the effect on the public is that it demonises an entire people, in this case the Russians, as being uniquely barbaric and savage. It creates simplistic stereotypes that lead people to emotional, rather than rational, interpretation of the conflict, and from this to support for emotional responses (“no negotiation”, “the villains must be punished”, etc.) that play into escalatory, hawkish political policy. Such policies are the worst possible position to take in regard to reducing the level of sexual violence in conflict. Narratives which paint a single side as being solely responsible for crimes that are commonly committed by all parties in a conflict, only serve to create entrenchment of views and a desire for retribution that will stymie efforts to reach negotiated settlements.

Setting aside any broader political or ethical questions regarding the war: which side is justified in their actions, what illegalities may have occurred, who should or should not achieve victory, etc., where supporting victims is the paramount aim for either governments or non-government organisations, efforts to portray one party’s crimes as more widespread or more serious in nature than another party, is counterproductive. A sincere desire to bring about peace cannot be advanced by extreme and inaccurate positions or the adoption of a simplistically black and white morality. An acceptance of some measure of joint culpability, and responsibility for harm done to civilians, is a key step in reaching common ground from which a more neutral and nonpartisan process for responding to this problem can begin.

In Closing

While definitive proof of politicisation is, barring explicit admission of intent, an impossible bar to reach, by looking at the patterns of coverage of the relevant issues it becomes reasonable to say, first that politicisation appears to be taking place, and secondly, that where it happens it will have a negative impact upon the clear understanding of and responses to problems of conflict-based sexual violence in Ukraine. Given this, it should be incumbent upon those who have a sincere desire to support the well-being of those affected, whether governments, NGOs, academics, or the general public, to pay greater attention to, and to address, instances in which further politicisation may occur.

What we can clearly state so far is that many of the earliest and most hyperbolic of claims were based upon apocryphal stories spread by high level officials without any supporting evidence. That many of the reports from organisations investigating the problem have been based upon the lowest standards of evidence and potentially biased in their interaction or lack thereof with the governments on either side of the conflict. Despite this, these reports have been widely promoted by the media in a manner suggesting that clear and reliable evidence of widespread and one-sided violations exists. We can also reliably state that both the political and media responses have shown a stronger focus on the demonisation and need for punishment of perpetrators (on one side), than they have focused on the actual well-being of victims in the conflict zone, or the welfare of vulnerable female refugees.

Recognition of politicisation is in no way an argument for less attention to be paid to Russian crimes of sexual violence. These have certainly occurred, and they warrant a proper judicial response. Rather, such recognition suggests that there may be an excessive focus on punishment of perpetrators rather than support for victims, that some victims might not be recognised, that others might be pressured to alter their testimony to fit political narratives, and that some perpetrators may be effectively given a blank pass due to the political inconvenience of their crimes.

To address such concerns a higher level of neutrality should be adhered to in the undertaking of investigation into and reporting of crimes of sexual violence. There is also a need for a greater and more open acknowledgement of the factors which can create conscious or unconscious bias in the investigatory and reporting processes. Sexual violence is a powerful, emotive crime, making it an obvious target for political manipulation. Properly approached, responses to this issue can be a pathway for overcoming the bitter enmities of conflict by reminding us of the commonalities of harm, suffering, and recovery that all civilian populations experience during conflict. A more robust framework for investigation of conflict-based sexual violence, which takes into account the very real danger of politicisation, needs to be adopted by organisations with a non-partisan desire to help and support survivors of such crimes.

References

- Amnesty. (2020). Not a private matter: Domestic and sexual violence against women in Eastern Ukraine. Amnesty International.
- Barber, H. (2022a). Castration, gang-rape, forced nudity: How Russia's soldiers terrorise Ukraine with sexual violence. *The Telegraph*, 28 November.
- Barber, H. (2022b). The hunt for Putin's war rapists: How a British-led team are tracking Russian perpetrators. *The Telegraph*, 22 December.
- BBC. (2022a). Ukraine conflict: 'Russian soldiers raped me and killed my husband'. BBC, 11 April.
- BBC. (2022b). Krasovsky: Russia bans 'burn Ukrainian kids' TV presenter., 24 October.
- Beltz, Amanda. (2008). Prosecuting rape in international criminal tribunals: The need to balance victim's rights with the due process rights of the accused. *Journal of Civil Rights and Economic Development*, 23 (1): 167–209.
- Boyd-Barrett, O. (2022). *Conflict Propaganda in Syria: Narrative Battles*. Routledge.
- Cimino, F., and Degani, P. (2023). Gendered impacts of the war in Ukraine: identifying potential, presumed or actual women victims of trafficking at the Italian borders. *Frontiers in Human Dynamics*, 5, 30 June.
- CJE. (2022). Regarding the behavior of Fakhruddin Sharafmal on the air of 24 TV channel. Ukrainian Commission for Journalistic Ethics, 17 March 2022.
- Clark, N. (2003). How the battle lies were drawn. *The Spectator*, 14 June.
- CNN. (2022). Russia using rape as 'military strategy' in Ukraine: UN envoy. CNN, 15 October.
- Coffey, L. (2022). Preparing for the Final Collapse of the Soviet Union and the Dissolution of the Russian Federation. *The Hudson Institute*, 14 December.
- Cross, M.E. (2018). The standard of proof on international investigation, in Bergsmo, M. and Stahn, C. (eds), *Quality Control in Preliminary Examination: Volume 2*, Torkel Opsahl Academic EPublisher.
- Doja, A. (2019). Politics of mass rapes in ethnic conflict: A morphodynamics of raw madness and cooked evil. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 71 (5), pp.541-580.
- EUCfCI. (2019). *War without rules: Gender-based violence in the context of the armed conflict in Eastern Ukraine*. Eastern Ukrainian Centre for Civic Initiatives.
- Ferris-Rotman, A. (2022). Ukrainians are speaking up about rape as a war crime to ensure the world holds Russia accountable. *Time*, 20 April.
- Fischer, H. (2022). How technology is being used to combat human trafficking. *Thomson Reuters*, 26 July.
- Frolov, P. (2022). Facebook post on 31st May 2022. Referenced online on 18th June 2023 at <https://www.facebook.com/pavlo.frolov.5/posts/pfbid0mGA723uTzjbTzVrowdPJnZUWsGchf65W1Sk4D6q64q7vc7VYBG4UBA3qzBvk8VEW1>
- Gebhardt, M. (2017). *Crimes unspoken: The rape of German women at the end of the Second World War*. Polity.
- Hathaway, O. (2022). A crime in search of a court: How to hold Russia accountable. *Foreign Affairs*, 19 May.
- Hathaway, O. (2023). Russia's crime and punishment: How to prosecute the illegal war in Ukraine. *Foreign Affairs*, 17 January.
- Helic, A. (2022). The world can't ignore Russia's use of rape as a weapon of war. *The Telegraph*, 31 March.
- Hill, P. (2019). Listen to us: Girls and boys gendered experiences of the conflict in Eastern Ukraine. *Save the Children*.
- HRW. (2018). North Korea: Sexual violence against women by officials. *Human Rights Watch*. 1 November.
- ICC. (2023). Situation in Ukraine: ICC judges issue arrest warrants against Vladimir Vladimirovich Putin and Maria Alekseyevna Lvova-Belova. *International Criminal Court*, 17 March.
- Jankowicz, M. (2022). Ukraine says it received more than 400 reports of sexual violence, including rape, by Russian soldiers within 2 weeks. *Yahoo News*, 27 April.
- Kasparov, G., and Khodorovsky, M. (2023). Don't fear Putin's demise: victory for Ukraine, democracy for Russia. *Foreign Affairs*, 20 January.
- Kolmasova, S, and Krulisova, K. (2019). Legitimizing military action through "rape-as-a-weapon" discourse in Libya: Critical feminist analysis. *Politics & Gender*, 15 (1): 130-50.
- Lapin, A. (2022). Украинский генерал пообещал убивать русских женщин и детей (Ukrainian general promised to kill Russian women and children). *Polit Navigator*, 18 March.
- Loffredo, J., and Blumenthal, M. (2023). ICC's Putin arrest warrant based on State Dept-funded report that debunked itself. *The Grayzone*, 31 March.
- Lukashova, S. (2022). Від facebook до допитів. Чому омбудсмен Денісова втратила посаду (From facebook to

- interrogations. Why did ombudsman Denisova lose her position?). *Ukrayinska Pravda*, 27 June.
- Madenholm, T. (2022). Rape as an ancient weapon of war. *Haartz*, 30 August.
- Marquis, A.G. (1978). Words as weapons: Propaganda in Britain and Germany during the First World War. *Journal of Contemporary History*, 13 (3). pp. 467-498.
- Meger, Sara. 2016. The fetishization of sexual violence in International security. *International Studies Quarterly*, 60 (1): 149-59.
- Mohan, M. (2017). Rape and no periods in North Korea's army. *BBC*. 21 November.
- Morris, L. (2022). She was raped in Ukraine. How many others have stories like hers? *Washington Post*, June 8.
- Ochab, E.U. (2022). United Nations: Rape is part of Russia's military strategy. *Forbes*, 14 October.
- OHCHR (2022a). The situation of human rights in Ukraine in the context of the armed attack by the Russian Federation, 24 February to 15 May 2022. United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 29 June.
- OHCHR. (2022b). Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine. United Nations Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights. 18 October.
- OHCHR. (2023) Report on the human rights situation in Ukraine, 1 August 2022 to 31 January 2023. United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 24 March.
- OSCE. (2019). *Добробут І: Безпека жінок: Україна - Доповідь про результати дослідження (Dobrobut 1: Safety of Women: Ukraine - Report on Research Results)*. OSCE.
- PBS (2021). 100% of Military sexual assault survivors feel 'trapped,' have suicidal ideations. *PBS News Hour*, 7 July.
- Pierre, H. (2018). Rape and strategy. *Inflexions*, 2 (38). pp. 173-180.
- Pravda. (2022). Захарова: ООН молчить о сексуальном рабстве беженков с України в Європе (Zakharova: the UN is silent about the sexual slavery of refugees from Ukraine in Europe). *Pravda*, 3 December.
- Rahman, D. (2022). Russia uses sexual violence as a weapon in Ukraine war: Official. *Rudaw News Network*, 25 May.
- Read, J.M. (1938). Atrocity propaganda and the Irish Rebellion. *The Public Opinion Quarterly*, 2 (2). pp. 229-244.
- Reuters. (2022). Foreign Minister accuses Russian soldiers of rape in Ukrainian cities. *Reuters*, 4 March.
- Reuters. (2023). Reactions to ICC's arrest warrant for Putin citing Ukraine war crimes. *Reuters*, 18 March.
- RMFA. (2022a). Response of MFA Spokesperson Maria Zakharova to a media question in connection with the statements of the Special Representative of the UN Secretary General on Sexual Violence in Conflicts. Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 16 October.
- RMFA. (2022b). Briefing by MFA Spokesperson Maria Zakharova, Moscow, October 20, 2022. Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 20 October.
- Rubenstein, A. (2022). UN envoy admits fabricating claim of Viagra-fueled rape as 'Russian military strategy'. *The Grayzone*, 13 November.
- Saletan, W. (2004). Rape rooms: A chronology. *Slate*, 5 May.
- Schrivers, P. (2005). *The GI war against Japan: American soldiers in Asia and the Pacific during World War II*. NYU Press.
- Scott, G. (2022). Russia's 'systematic' use of rape in Ukraine is a war crime, says Olena Zelenska. *The Times of London*, 28 November.
- Siddiqui, Z. (2022). Can Putin actually face accountability at the ICC. *Foreign Policy*, 4 May.
- Simic, O. (2016). Rape, silence, and denial, in Fischer, M. and Simic, O. (eds) *Transitional justice and reconciliation: Lessons from the Balkans*. Routledge.
- Szewczyk, B.M.J. (2023). Europe needs a strategy for Russia after Putin. *Foreign Policy*, 20 January.
- Sluga Naroda. (2022). Парламент дозволив воювати тим, кому обрано запобіжний захід (The parliament allowed those who were placed under preventive measures to fight). *Sluga Naroda*, 13 March.
- Sonnenfeld, J. (2022). How to take down a tyrant. *Foreign Policy*, 10 August.
- Sussman, A.L. (2011). Is rape inevitable in war? *The Atlantic*, 26 May.
- Taylor, C. (2022). Ukrainian women are reporting rape by Russian soldiers but is it a war crime, a crime against humanity or even genocide? *ABC (AUS)*, 4 July.
- UKFCDO. (2014). *International protocol on the documentation and investigation of sexual violence in conflict: Basic standards of best practice on the documentation of sexual Violence as a crime under international law*. United Kingdom Foreign, Commonwealth and development Office.
- UKFCDO. (2022). *Preventing sexual violence in conflict initiative strategy*. United Kingdom Foreign Commonwealth and Development Office, 28 November.

- UKGov. (2022). Preventing Sexual Violence in Conflict Initiative conference 2022: Foreign Secretary's speech. UK Government, 28 November.
- UNHCR. (2017). Conflict-related sexual violence in Ukraine, 14 March 2014 to 31 January 2017. United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights.
- UPCFHR. (2022). Lyudmila Denisova reported another case of sexual violence with striking brutality by the Russian military. Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights, 22 May.
- USSD. (2023). Evidence of Russia's War Crimes and Other Atrocities in Ukraine: Recent Reporting on Child Relocations. US State Department, 31 March.
- Vox. (2022). False: Liudmila Denisova admitted to lying about rapes committed against Ukrainians by Russian occupiers. Vox Ukraine, 30 June.
- Wamsley, L. (2022). Rape has reportedly become a weapon in Ukraine. Finding justice may be difficult. NPR, 30 April.
- Wenner Moyer, M. (2021). A poison in the system: The epidemic of military sexual assault. New York Times, 3 August.
- Zurn, M. (2019). Politicization compared: at national, European, and global levels. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26 (7).